

ENHANCED MACHINE LEARNING CLASSIFICATION WITH WEIGHTED LOSS PENALTY ON CREDIT CARD FRAUD DETECTION

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides an innovative approach for data imbalance handling, namely partial penalty, to enhance the machine learning application in credit card fraud detection field. Such approach avoids the misleading data or data missing issue brought by traditional over-sampling or under-sampling approaches, keeps the training data same as validation and testing data, and realizes a higher performance in both validation and testing scenarios. Under the partial penalty methodology, we've also applied five machine learning models, including Logistic Regression, Random Forest, kNN, Decision Tree, and Light Gradient Boosting, and achieves 88.35% F1 score and 98.79% AUC score in testing scenario.

KEYWORDS

Partial Penalty, Gradient Boosting, Data Imbalance, Credit Card Fraud Detection, SMOTE

1. INTRODUCTION

Increasing from 18.18% of all transactions in 2016 to 32.61% of all transactions in 2023 in the US, credit card payment has been becoming one of the most dominant payment methods amount all consumer transactions [1]. While cash accounted for only 14% of all US consumer payments in 2024, credit cards occupied higher proportion and accounted for 35%, representing over 65% of all payments after combined with debit cards payment [2]. Such an increase in the volume of credit card transactions has caused the significantly higher credit card fraud risk, or the unauthorized use of credit card or debit card information to make withdrawals or purchases, typically including physical card theft, online theft, application fraud by using others' personal information, and account takeover transactions [3]. According to Federal Trade Commission's consumer sentinel network data book (2024), the number of complaints of identity theft related to existing credit card misuse or new card applications has increased from 416,582 to 449,032 in 2024, counting for \$12.5 billion in total consumer loss [4].

However, when it comes to credit card fraud detection, there're many challenges to be solved, including advanced fraud technologies such as biometrics to bypass traditional security measures, the increasing volume of daily fraud transactions, or balancing the transaction security measures and customer experience [5]. While implementing machine learning could solve some of the challenges and improve the efficiency, the data imbalance issue is the key challenge that prevents machine learning model to be able to capture true fraud transactions (usually less than 1%). This article provides an innovative way that could handle such extreme data imbalance issue while outperform the traditional over sampling and under sampling approaches.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Because truly fraudulent transactions represent only a very small proportion of the vast number of legitimate credit card transactions, machine learning has been increasingly adopted to identify these rare events more efficiently and reduce reliance on labor-intensive manual review and rigid monitoring rules. Several prior studies have applied machine learning methods to the same European credit card fraud dataset used in this article. For instance, ensemble approaches incorporating models such as SVM, kNN, and boosting-based algorithms have achieved an AUC score of 96% on this dataset [6].

In earlier work published in 2022, researchers also evaluated the use of a SaaS platform for model training and testing in credit card fraud detection, reporting a recall of 84% and an AUC score of 97.3% on the test dataset [7].

In addition, feature selection techniques have been investigated through combinations of linear correlation, Information Gain, and random forest feature importance to identify the most relevant predictors [8]. Alternative feature reduction methods, including ANOVA, were likewise examined by Xiaomei Feng and Song-Kyoo Kim to reduce dimensionality and improve fraud detection performance [9].

Besides the choice of machine learning models and feature engineering, data imbalance handling is another important component for credit card fraud detection model performance. Based on the research conducted by Nazim Uddin Niaz, imbalanced data could cause the machine learning model to be more influenced by majority class while neglecting the minority class [10].

Over-sampling methodology, such as SMOTE, has been proved to increase the fraud detection model performance by creating similar data points to balance the minor target class with the major class in training data [11]. Under-sampling methodology has been compared with oversampling showing different levels of supportive effects on different machine learning algorithms, of which the F-1 score could be increased to 87% [12].

3. METHODOLOGY

This article aims to investigate a novel methodology that adjusts classification penalties between minority and majority target classes to encourage machine learning models to place greater emphasis on detecting the minority class during training.

This approach is further integrated with hyperparameter tuning, oversampling techniques, and k-fold cross-validation to present a comprehensive assessment of the performance gains achieved at each stage of the analytical workflow, as well as the associated training time. The overall analysis process applied in this study is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Analysis flow including (1) Imbalance data handling (2) Model tuning (3) Model evaluation

In this analysis, we’ve used the masked real-world September 2013 European Credit Card Fraud dataset collected by Worldline and the Machine Learning Group of ULB (Université Libre de Bruxelles) on big data mining and fraud detection. [13]. The original dataset has recorded 284,807 real transactions including 492 (0.17%) fraud transactions as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Original dataset fraud distribution (1) Credit card fraud transactions: 492 (0.17%) of all transactions (2) Credit card non-fraud transactions: 284,315 (99.83%) of all transactions.

3.1. Partial Penalty

The major challenge of Credit Card Fraud detection is the scarcity of the positive fraud records. Without proper data imbalance handling, machine learning models may simply predict most transactions as negative to realize a falsely high accuracy while sacrifices the prediction power of capturing the true fraud transactions.

To handle such target class imbalance, over-sampling, such as SMOTE, and under-sampling can be implemented to either artificially create unreal data points to expand minor class or remove real data points to reduce major class [14].

However, both paths have their own risks. Over-sampling can bring in unrealistic noises into training data that may not happen in testing environment, while under-sampling can face the risk of losing massive amounts of real information by aggressively removing major target class data points.

The conceptual differences among over-sampling, under-sampling, and partial penalty implementation can be visualized as below:

Figure 3. Over-sampling, under-sampling, and partial penalty implementation.

As shown in Figure 3, over-sampling methodology creates fake training data, labelled as orange, to balance the volume between minor and major classes while under-sampling methodology removes majority of training data.

However, partial penalty approach keeps the training data untouched, while give higher weight to false prediction penalty in minor class prediction. To be specifically, the loss function in this binary classification prediction is shown as below:

$$L = -w \sum_{i=1}^C y_i \log \hat{y}_i$$

Where C is the number of classes, y_i is true labels (1 or 0), and \hat{y}_i is the predicted probability from classification model. The w coefficient will increase the magnitude of loss value from false prediction in minor classes to make the model give more attention to the minor class learning proportionally.

In this study, to keep the training data as close to the real-world environment as possible, an innovative solution is proposed to train the machine learning models by partially customizing the model's penalty weight on minor target class. Because the ratio between major class and minor class in this data is $284,315 / 492 = 577.87$, we will implement 577.87 times penalty weight on fraud prediction and 1 time penalty weight on non-fraud prediction.

3.2. Hyper parameter Tuning

After keeping the training data distribution the same as that of testing data, we continue to explore the best hyperparameters within class weighted models, including Logistic Regression (LR), Random Forest (RF), k Nearest Neighbor (kNN), Decision Tree (DT) and Light Gradient

Boosting Model (LGB), to study how hyper parameter would impact class weighted machine learning models in credit card detection.

According to Annika Stuke's research, Bayesian Optimization hyper parameter tuning algorithms performs better than other tuning algorithms, especially in the computing speed and high dimension prediction [15]. Because our credit card fraud data has 25 dimensions with a relatively wide initial range of continuous hyper parameter values, we've decided to use Bayesian Optimization to tune the hyper parameters as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Hyperparameter tuning selection range

Model	Hyperparameter Range
LR	tol:(0, 1), C:(0, 1), l1_ratio:(0, 1), max_iter:(100, 300)
RF	max_depth:(5, 15), min_impurity_decrease:(0, 1e-6), min_samples_leaf:(1, 10), n_estimators:(300, 400)
kNN	n_neighbors:(3, 100), algorithm:(('auto', 'ball_tree', 'kd_tree'))
DT	max_depth:(1, 15), min_impurity_decrease:(0, 1e-6), min_samples_leaf:(1, 10)
LGB	max_depth:(5, 15), num_leaves:(200, 300), learning_rate:(0.01, 0.1), n_estimators:(300, 400)

3.3. Comparison with Sampling Methodologies

To evaluate the relative performance of oversampling, under-sampling, and class-weighted modelling, this study additionally applied the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) and an under-sampling method to the original training dataset, using the optimal hyperparameters identified in Section 3.2.

In addition to implementing only one method to deal with the data imbalance, we've also introduced the test group to hybrid the class weighted modelling process with the sampling methodologies so that we finally get the final 25 versions of models for performance comparison listed as in Table 2:

Table 2. Credit card fraud modelling methodologies

Methodology	Model	Class Weight	Sampling	Hyperparameter Tuning
LR NNN	LR	N/A	N/A	Not Tuned
RF NNN	RF			
kNN NNN	kNN			
DT NNN	DT			
LGB NNN	LGB			
LR WNN	LR	Weighted	N/A	Not Tuned
RF WNN	RF			
kNN WNN	kNN			
DT WNN	DT			
LGB WNN	LGB			
LR WNT	LR	Weighted	N/A	Tuned

RF WNT	RF		Over-Sampling	Tuned
kNN WNT	kNN			
DT WNT	DT			
LGB WNT	LGB			
LR NOT	LR			
RF NOT	RF	N/A	Under-Sampling	Tuned
kNN NOT	kNN			
DT NOT	DT			
LGB NOT	LGB			
LR NUT	LR			
RF NUT	RF	N/A	Under-Sampling	Tuned
kNN NUT	kNN			
DT NUT	DT			
LGB NUT	LGB			

3.4. Cross Validation

To evaluate the methodology performance without data leakage, we've selected a hybrid evaluation check by two steps:

- (1) Splitting the original dataset into 80% as training data and holding 20% as testing data
- (2) Cross validating each of the methodologies based on 5-fold cross validation on training data

Based on Janio Martinez Bachmann's evaluation results, to check the over-sampling and under-sampling methodologies without data leakage in the prediction results and over-fitting in the validation results, the sampling process should be implemented during the cross-validation not before cross-validation [16].

Figure 4. Over-Sampling during cross validation. For the whole training data, we split the data into 5 folds and within each iteration, we over-sampled the training data to train the model and predict based on real validation data.

Figure 5. Under-Sampling during cross validation. For the whole training data, we split the data into 5 folds and within each iteration, we under-sampled the training data to train the model and predict based on real validation data.

As shown in Figure 4 and 5, we've combined the cross-validation process with the over-sampling and under-sampling to implement the sampling to training data within each of the 5 iterations and predict on real validation data so that the cross-validation results contain only real data points to be compared with the actual real fraud data points.

3.5. Evaluation Metrics

To understand the model prediction performance of credit card fraud in different aspects, we've used 5 evaluation metrics: ROC_AUC, Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F-1 score.

- (1) ROC_AUC (Receiver Operating Characteristic – Area Under the Curve) is the area under the ROC curve to represent the true positive rate against the false positive rate at various classification thresholds.
- (2) Accuracy is the metric to measure how much percentage of testing target is correctly predicted by the classification model.
- (3) Precision is the metric to measure how much percentage of positive predictions (Credit Card Fraud = 1) are actual positive results.
- (4) Recall is the metric to measure how much percentage of positive results (Credit Card Fraud = 1) are correctly labelled by the classification model as positive.
- (5) F-1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall measuring the model's performance on positive prediction (Credit Card Fraud = 1), especially if the target variable is imbalanced.

We've applied the five-evaluation metrics to the 5-Fold cross validation results so that the evaluation results are stable without data leakage.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Partial Penalty And Hyper parameter Tuning

Using original dataset, class weighted partial penalty and hyper parameter tuning, we've observed the performance changes as in Figure 6 below:

Sampling	Hyperparameter	Modeling	accuracy_score	precision_score	recall_score	f1_score
Original-Data	Basic-Hyperparameter	Logistic Regression	0.999209	0.843636	0.648045	0.733017
		Random Forest	0.999593	0.944262	0.804469	0.868778
		kNN	0.999307	0.910156	0.650838	0.758958
		Decision Tree	0.999199	0.760446	0.762570	0.761506
		Light GBM	0.995950	0.221734	0.564246	0.318361
Class-Weighted	Basic-Hyperparameter	Logistic Regression	0.999363	0.818966	0.796089	0.807365
		Random Forest	0.999569	0.965035	0.770950	0.857143
		kNN	0.999345	0.922481	0.664804	0.772727
		Decision Tree	0.999265	0.786325	0.770950	0.778561
		Light GBM	0.999565	0.895522	0.837989	0.865801
	Hyperparameter-Tuned	Logistic Regression	0.999391	0.841317	0.784916	0.812139
		Random Forest	0.999490	0.865103	0.824022	0.844063
		kNN	0.999410	0.886667	0.743017	0.808511
		Decision Tree	0.999448	0.900000	0.754190	0.820669
		Light GBM	0.999640	0.963696	0.815642	0.883510

Figure 6. Performance improvement using sampling and hyper parameter tuning methodology

As shown in Figure 6, because of the imbalance in original data, machine learning models have relatively low precision, recall and F1 validation performance. For example, Light GBM provides the lowest 0.2217 precision, 0.5642 recall and 0.3183 F1 score among all five machine learning models.

However, after implementing the class-weighted methodology of partial penalty, all those five models' performances have been improved. For instance, the F1 score of Light GBM increased from 0.3183 to 0.8658 using partial penalty and 0.8835 after further combining hyperparameter tuning results.

The AUC curve-based performance for class-weighted partial penalty and hyperparameter tuning can be found in the following Figure 7–9.

Figure 7. Base model AUC performance.

Figure 8. Partial penalty AUC performance.

Figure 9. Partial penalty and hyper parameter tuned AUC performance.

Figure 7-9 provide us with a detailed visualization of ROC improvement from partial penalty and hyperparameter tuning. All five models' AUC have been improved, especially for tree-based models. For example, decision tree AUC score increased from 0.8853 to 0.9034, while Light GBM AUC score increased from 0.6882 to 0.9879.

As we can see in Figure 6 and 9, the best model after partial penalty and hyperparameter tuning is Light GBM, realizing 0.9637 precision, 0.8156 recall, 0.8835 F1 score, and 0.9879 AUC score.

4.2. Comparison with Sampling Methodologies

To compare with the other sampling methodologies, we've also conducted cross validation for the over-sampling (SMOTE) and under-sampling methodologies in addition to partial penalty while keeping the optimal hyperparameters the same.

The performance impact due to sampling strategy change can be found in Figure 10.

Sampling	Hyperparameter	Modeling	auc_score	accuracy_score	precision_score	recall_score	f1_score
Original-Data	Basic-Hyperparameter	Logistic Regression	0.951850	0.999190	0.829181	0.650838	0.729264
		Random Forest	0.951312	0.999583	0.943894	0.798883	0.865356
		kNN	0.895105	0.999307	0.910156	0.650838	0.758958
		Decision Tree	0.881083	0.999204	0.762570	0.762570	0.762570
		Light GBM	0.688185	0.995950	0.221734	0.564246	0.318361
Partial-Penalty	Hyperparameter-Tuned	Logistic Regression	0.983791	0.999340	0.835913	0.754190	0.792952
		Random Forest	0.983122	0.999073	0.675439	0.860335	0.756757
		kNN	0.895145	0.999410	0.886667	0.743017	0.808511
		Decision Tree	0.903360	0.999448	0.900000	0.754190	0.820669
		Light GBM	0.987899	0.999640	0.963696	0.815642	0.883510
Over-Sampling	Hyperparameter-Tuned	Logistic Regression	0.976744	0.999361	0.852654	0.780619	0.810948
		Random Forest	0.984225	0.998118	0.502423	0.845503	0.616069
		kNN	0.927478	0.987872	0.116249	0.844666	0.201683
		Decision Tree	0.867360	0.995597	0.249443	0.743537	0.368871
		Light GBM	0.983973	0.999319	0.817728	0.799014	0.805068
Under-Sampling	Hyperparameter-Tuned	Logistic Regression	0.966003	0.998589	0.633512	0.607543	0.615650
		Random Forest	0.976215	0.999361	0.857499	0.755516	0.798890
		kNN	0.942040	0.986377	0.136050	0.678623	0.211640
		Decision Tree	0.930044	0.940233	0.027787	0.890414	0.053563
		Light GBM	0.982840	0.999259	0.838275	0.703830	0.760178

Figure 10. Performance comparison. 20 models with baseline models, partial-penalty, over-sampling and under-sampling approaches.

As we can see in Figure 10, hyperparameter tuned combined with data imbalance adjustment methodologies, including partial penalty, over-sampling and under-sampling, have in general much better AUC and F1 score performances than baseline models without hyperparameter tuning. Out of all listed models, Light GBM with partial penalty methodology provides the best performance with 0.9879 AUC, 0.9996 accuracy, 0.9637 precision, 0.8156 recall and 0.8835 F1 score based on the cross validation.

The detailed ROC_AUC curves are listed in Figure 11 for four data imbalance adjustment methodologies along with the highest three AUC scores with each methodology.

Figure 11. AUC curve comparison with highest three AUC scores shown in the lower right corner of each segment.

As shown in Figure 11, while the best model in baseline situation is logistic regression, Light GBM has been improved using the right data imbalance adjustment methodologies and outperforms Logistic Regression model in partial penalty (0.988), over-sampling (0.984), and under-sampling (0.983) methodologies.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluates three distinct approaches for addressing extreme class imbalance in credit card fraud prediction: traditional over-sampling, under-sampling, and a novel partial-penalty method applied to the minority target class. To assess the effectiveness of these imbalance-handling strategies across different machine learning contexts, five classification algorithms were implemented under each approach, including Logistic Regression, Random Forest, kNN, Decision Tree, and LightGBM. Among the three methods, the partial-penalty approach demonstrated superior performance, achieving higher accuracy, ROC-AUC, precision, recall, and F1 scores than both over-sampling and under-sampling techniques. In particular, when combined with LightGBM, the partial-penalty method produced the strongest results, with an F1 score of 88.35% and an AUC score of 98.79%.

However, such study has its limitation on the size of data. The dataset used in this study contains 284,807 transaction records with 492 fraud transactions, which can be further expanded to larger amount of transaction from real world to better validate the stability of such partial penalty framework along with the light GBM.

In conclusion, this study investigates the benefits of using partial penalty framework to improve imbalanced data for machine learning prediction. In the results, such innovative work improved the F1 score performance by 8% compared to SMOTE approach and by 11% compared to under-sampling approach. Such new methodology has also shown an over improvement across five evaluation metrics and five machine learning classification models. Such result shows a promising result that can be potentially expanded and used in larger amount of data to validate and provide better contribution to machine learning data imbalance handling process.

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